

1 **Potential environmental and health impacts of EU Green Deal's Farm to Fork strategy**
2 **depend on consumption-side policies to promote dietary change**

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14 **Abstract**

15 **Background** The EU's Farm to Fork (F2F) policy framework targets production- and consumption-
16 side activities of the food system to facilitate the transition to net-zero by 2050. However, the
17 potential environmental and health impacts of its implementation are not known. Our objective was to
18 provide quantitative estimates for the joint environmental and health impacts of adopting F2F policies
19 in the EU.

20 **Methods** We used a food systems model to analyse changes in food intake and the related health and
21 environmental impacts for scenarios that achieved F2F production-side targets with or without
22 consumption-side policies for partial or complete shifts towards healthy and sustainable diets.
23 Environmental impacts were estimated based on food production quantities or their underlying
24 agricultural activities. We used a comparative risk assessment to estimate mortality impacts
25 attributable to diet- and weight-related risk factors in 2050.

26 **Findings** Reductions to environmental impacts from production-side policies were reinforced by
27 targeted dietary changes. Partial and complete adoption of healthy and sustainable diets decreased
28 total mortality by 11% and 14%, respectively, compared to 0.2% from production-side policies alone.
29 Most gains were attributable to reductions in coronary heart disease and cancer (up to 380 and 313
30 thousand, respectively) from changes in vegetable intake and obesity (up to ~230 thousand each). The
31 greatest proportion of averted deaths was for Eastern Europe (up to 22%).

32 **Interpretation** Adopting F2F policies with targeted dietary shifts resulted in the greatest co-benefits
33 for environmental and health outcomes. To realise the environmental and health co-benefits of food
34 system decarbonisation, stronger initiatives are needed to facilitate consumer shifts towards healthy
35 and sustainable diets.

36 **Funding** European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant
37 agreement no. 101057131 (CATALYSE).

38 **Introduction**

39 Adopted in 2020 as part of the European Green Deal, the Farm to Fork (F2F) strategy is a set of
40 policies that aim to foster fair, healthy, and sustainable food systems and achieving net-zero by mid-
41 century. The strategy outlines quantitative targets for production-side interventions while encouraging
42 the shift towards healthy and sustainable diets, and fostering global cooperation in efforts towards
43 transforming food systems through international trade.¹ A report released in 2025 by the Joint
44 Research Commission revealed that while the European Union (EU) is on track to meeting two of the
45 seven quantifiable F2F targets, progress on the transition to healthy and sustainable diets could not be
46 assessed due to a lack of adequate indicators and harmonized dietary data.² Defining appropriate
47 indicators and curating the necessary data underpinning those indicators is central to guiding policies
48 that incentivize consumers to make healthier and more sustainable food choices.

49 Studies have consistently shown that diets containing more fruits, vegetables, whole grains, and plant-
50 based protein sources and less red and processed meat are associated with lower risks of chronic
51 diseases³ and diet-related environmental impacts.⁴ However, dietary patterns generally do not adhere
52 to recommendations for healthy and sustainable diets. In Europe, nearly one-third of deaths were
53 attributable to dietary risk factors in 2017⁵, while consumption of meat and dairy accounted for the
54 majority of diet-related greenhouse gas emissions (40% and 18%, respectively) and land use impacts
55 (53% and 14%, respectively).⁶ The proposed shift towards plant-based diets in the F2F strategy could
56 make important contributions for improving health and reducing environmental impacts.

57 While several studies have analysed the potential impacts of F2F policies, none have integrated
58 production and consumption perspectives in assessing health outcomes. Most studies have focused
59 exclusively on supply-side mitigation measures, with little to no accounting of demand-side changes
60 relating to diets and reductions in food loss and waste⁷⁻¹¹, while those that integrated production- and
61 consumption-side policies did not assess health outcomes explicitly.¹²⁻¹⁶ Importantly, these
62 assessments have shown that policies could have opposing effects when modelled in isolation rather
63 than in combination.¹⁵ Understanding the potential impacts stemming from production- and

64 consumption-side policies in the F2F strategy is needed to identify synergies and trade-offs to better
65 inform decision-making.

66 Here, our objective was to provide quantitative estimates of potential environmental and health
67 impacts from adopting F2F policies in the EU, including a shift towards healthy and sustainable diets.
68 We used a food systems model of the agricultural sector to estimate how dietary intakes and
69 environmental impacts would change from the regional adoption of F2F production-side policies with
70 or without partial or complete shifts towards healthy and sustainable diets. We then used comparative
71 risk assessment to estimate the potential reductions in premature mortality by 2050 compared to a
72 counterfactual scenario in which F2F policies were not adopted. To account for the EU's commitment
73 to international cooperation in the global transition towards sustainable food systems, we estimated
74 global environmental and health impacts in a sensitivity analysis for two additional scenarios where
75 non-EU countries adopted half of the EU's shifts towards healthy and sustainable diets.

76

77 **Methods**

78 *Food systems model*

79 We used a food systems model to capture the effects of F2F policies on dietary intakes and
80 environmental impacts. Food systems models are computational models that allow for assessing the
81 interactions among activities and actors in the food supply chain in response to 'shocks' (e.g.,
82 policies). We used the Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact (CAPRI) model, a partial
83 equilibrium model of the agricultural sector commonly used to inform agricultural, environmental,
84 and trade policies in the EU and globally.¹⁷ CAPRI combines a regional supply model that consists of
85 55 agricultural inputs for crop and livestock production, with a global market model that responds to
86 supply, demand, and price changes for 65 agricultural commodities and processed products
87 considering multilateral trade. The data on food consumption in CAPRI comes from FAOSTAT and
88 Eurostat. The model solves for a market equilibrium where global supply equals demand. More
89 information on CAPRI is in the Supplementary Information.

90 *Scenario development*

91 We developed model representations of F2F policies that met production-side targets with or without
92 consumption-side targets for healthy and sustainable diets. The production-side policies modelled in
93 CAPRI were a 50% reduction in nitrogen surplus; a 20% reduction in mineral fertilisers; at least a
94 30% reduction in pesticides; a 25% increase in land under organic farming; and having 10% of
95 agricultural land with high-diversity landscape features (e.g., non-rotational fallow land). In line with
96 the overarching Green Deal, we also incorporated carbon pricing in our scenarios since these could
97 apply to the agricultural sector which could in turn influence food prices and consumption changes.
98 Since the European Commission did not propose quantitative targets for consumption-side policies,
99 we assumed graded shifts towards healthy and sustainable diets using the EAT-Lancet Commission's
100 planetary health diet. The planetary health diet emphasizes consumption of fruits, vegetables, whole
101 grains, legumes, and nuts, and optional moderate amounts of meat and dairy products.¹⁸ Since the F2F
102 strategy also aims to address rising rates of overweight and obesity and food waste, we additionally
103 applied reductions in total energy intake and food waste in the scenarios with targeted dietary
104 changes. Total energy intake was specific to each country, and the reductions reflected balanced
105 energy intake based on requirements for optimal bodyweight considering each country's age and sex
106 structure and assuming moderate levels of physical activity.¹⁹

107 We incorporated the various aspects of F2F policies into four scenarios: the reference scenario
108 represented the expected food system trajectories before publication of the Green Deal and observed
109 diets; the F2F scenario included a low carbon price and production-side targets for nitrogen,
110 fertilisers, pesticides, organic farming, and land use without targeted dietary changes; F2F-50
111 included a low carbon price, F2F production-side targets, and a 50% shift towards healthy and
112 sustainable diets, including balanced energy intake and a 15% reduction in food waste; and F2F-100
113 included a high carbon price, F2F production-side targets, and a 100% shift towards healthy and
114 sustainable diets, including balanced energy intake and a 20% reduction in food waste. The scenarios
115 are in Table 1 and described further in the Supplementary Information.

116 To account for the EU's commitment to international collaboration in achieving global climate
117 targets, we considered two additional multilateral scenarios – F2F-50m and F2F-100m – in which
118 non-EU countries adopted half of the EU's carbon price and shifts towards healthy and sustainable
119 diets in the F2F-50 and F2F-100 scenarios (Supplementary Information).

120 *Environmental impacts*

121 Environmental impacts were estimated in CAPRI based on food production quantities or their
122 underlying agricultural activities.¹⁷ In some cases, agricultural activities served directly as
123 environmental indicators (e.g., land use). Pesticide use was crop-specific and dependent on crop
124 yields. Nutrient surpluses were estimated through nutrient balancing equations for crops with main
125 input sources being mineral fertilisers and manure, and main sinks being crop needs and total losses.
126 GHG and ammonia emissions were calculated by multiplying activity levels by emission factors,
127 which were calculated for the cattle sector based on IPCC Tier 2 methodology (considering the feed
128 mix).

129 *Health impacts*

130 We used a comparative risk assessment framework to estimate the mortality impacts from dietary
131 changes in each scenario. Comparative risk assessment is used for estimating changes in disease
132 burden attributable to selected risk factors given a change in exposure to those risk factors in a
133 population over time.²⁰ We estimated the number of deaths that could be avoided by indirect dietary
134 changes in the F2F scenario, and by targeted dietary shifts in the F2F-50 and F2F-100 scenarios
135 compared to the reference scenario. We accounted for eight diet-related (low intake of fruits,
136 vegetables, nuts and seeds, and legumes, and high intake of red meat) and weight-related risk factors
137 (underweight, overweight, or obese) and five disease endpoints (coronary heart disease, stroke, type 2
138 diabetes, cancer, and respiratory disease). We selected risk factors based on moderate to high levels of
139 evidence of associations with chronic diseases from meta-analyses of cohort studies (Supplementary
140 Information). We included non-linear dose-response relationships for fruits and vegetables and nuts

141 and seeds, and linear dose-response relationships for the remaining risk factors in line with meta-
142 analyses. The relative risks are in Supplementary Table S1.

143 Baseline data on weight distributions were from the Non-Communicable Disease Risk Factor
144 Collaboration²¹, and weight changes in the scenarios were estimated based on the relationship
145 between BMI and total energy intake as done previously.²² We aggregated relative risks for BMI
146 categories (underweight: <18.5 kg/m²; overweight: 25 to 29.9 kg/m²; and obese: 30-39.9 kg/m²) and
147 normalized to a risk-neutral normal weight category (18.5 to 24.9 kg/m²) consistent with evidence
148 from epidemiological studies.^{23,24} We focused our analysis on individuals aged 20 y and older since
149 we were interested in mortality from diet-related chronic diseases which mainly affect adults, and we
150 included age effects for risks becoming attenuated with age.²⁵ To estimate averted deaths, we
151 combined risks with population data from the United Nations Population Division²⁶ and mortality data
152 for from the Global Burden of Disease project²⁷ for the years of the analysis. The lower and upper
153 confidence intervals of the relative risk were used for error propagation. We present results for 2050
154 since that is the year in which the net-zero objective of the Green Deal is intended to be met. More
155 details on comparative risk assessment are in the Supplementary Information.

156

157 **Role of the funding source:** The funder had no role in the study design, collection, analysis, and
158 interpretation of the data, or writing of the report.

159

160 **Results**

161 *Environmental impacts*

162 Reductions in environmental impacts were generally greater in scenarios where production-side
163 policies were accompanied by dietary changes (Table 2). GHG emissions decreased by 26% in the
164 F2F scenario, and by ~30% in the F2F-50 and F2F-100 scenarios. Reductions in nitrogen surplus were
165 ~50% across scenarios due to reductions in the use of mineral fertilisers as evidenced from decreases

166 in phosphorus surplus (39% to 47%) and ammonia emissions (23% to 32%). Reductions in
167 phosphorus surplus and ammonia emissions were 6% to 9% greater in the F2F-50 and F2F-100
168 scenarios compared to F2F due reductions in meat intake. There were small increases in agricultural
169 land use since less agricultural land was available with increasing non-productive landscape elements
170 (i.e., share of fallow land in utilizable agricultural area) and the reductions to fertilisers which requires
171 more land to be farmed at a lower intensity, but these were smaller in scenarios with intentional
172 dietary changes (F2F: 3.1%; F2F-50 and F2F-100: 1.9% each).

173 *Changes in diet and weight composition*

174 The contribution of food groups to diet composition increased for plant-based foods and decreased for
175 animal-based foods in EU countries (EU27) across the scenarios (Figure 1 and Supplementary Table
176 S2). Changes in food intake were greatest for F2F-50 and F2F-100, and comparable between F2F and
177 the reference scenario. In F2F-50, intakes decreased most for dairy (−75 g/d; −24%), pork (−33 g/d;
178 −44%), and sugar (−30 g/d; −32%), and increased most for vegetables (+97 g/d; +81%), legumes (+31
179 g/d; +370%), and fruits (+22 g/d; +40%). Changes for fish and roots were small (<2 g/d). Changes
180 were generally proportional in the F2F-100 scenario. The percentage of the population with obesity
181 decreased by 12 to 13 percentage points in the F2F-50 and F2F-100 scenarios, while the percentage
182 that were overweight decreased by 5 to 6 percentage points. There was a small percentage of the
183 population in the underweight category in all scenarios.

184 Changes in diet and weight composition varied between EU27 countries in line with reference diets
185 (Supplementary Figure S1). Among risk factors in F2F-50, changes in vegetable intake ranged from
186 +13 g/d (+9%) in Cyprus to +173 g/d in Ireland and the Netherlands (+321% and +282%,
187 respectively); fruits from +1 g/d in Luxemburg, Belgium, and Estonia (up to +2%) to +54 g/d in
188 Poland (+122%); legumes from +7 g/d in Latvia (+6%) to +42 g/d in Czechia (+877%); nuts and
189 seeds from −1 g/d Romania (−2%) to +20 g/d in Hungary (+431%); and red meat from −26 g/d in
190 Latvia (−40%) to −84 g/d in Denmark (−47%). Changes in overweight and obesity prevalence were

191 greatest for France (–10 percentage points and –20 percentage points, respectively) and smallest for
192 Slovakia (+0.1 percentage points and +0.2 percentage points, respectively).

193 *Health impacts*

194 We estimated that 98% of potential reductions in premature mortality were attributable to targeted
195 dietary changes as opposed to indirect changes stemming from production-side policies. The F2F-50
196 and F2F-100 scenarios led to 637 thousand (95% confidence interval (CI): 620 thousand, 653
197 thousand) and 811 thousand (95% CI: 784 thousand, 838 thousand) averted deaths by mid-century, an
198 11% and 14% reduction in total deaths, respectively. Averted deaths brought on by changes to
199 production practices only (the F2F scenario) were smaller (13.9 thousand (95% CI: 13.4 thousand,
200 14.4 thousand); 0.2% of total deaths). Nearly half of all averted deaths in the F2F-50 and F2F-100
201 scenarios were attributable to reductions in coronary heart disease and 39% to cancer (Figure 2a),
202 with largest contributions from changes in vegetable intake (F2F-50: 159 thousand (95% CI: 153
203 thousand, 165 thousand); F2F-100: 233 thousand (95% CI: 223 thousand, 244 thousand)) and obesity
204 (F2F-50: 254 thousand (95% CI: 259 thousand, 259 thousand); F2F-100: 230 thousand (95% CI: 225
205 thousand, 235 thousand)) (Figure 2b).

206 Averted deaths for EU27 countries ranged from 0.7 to 2.5 per 1000 people in F2F-50 and 1 to 3.3 per
207 1000 people in F2F-100 (Figure 3, Supplementary Table S3, and Supplementary Figure S2). In both
208 scenarios, averted deaths were greatest for countries in Eastern and Northern Europe, including
209 Czechia (2.5 to 3.3 per 1000 people) and Lithuania (2.6 to 3.2 per 1000 people), and lowest for Malta
210 (0.7 to 1 per 1000 people) and Cyprus (0.9 to 1.2 per 1000 people). Countries with the highest rates of
211 averted deaths could be attributable to a combination of risk factors – mainly greater intake of
212 vegetables, legumes, and lower prevalence of obesity – but also higher underlying death rates.

213 *Sensitivity analysis based on multilateral scenarios*

214 Our sensitivity analysis in which non-EU countries adopted half of the EU27's carbon price and shifts
215 towards healthy and sustainable diets in the F2F-50 and F2F-100 scenarios led to large reductions to
216 global environmental impacts. Global reductions in GHG emissions were between 49.3% and 60% in
217 the multilateral scenarios. The percentage change for other indicators was similar to those for the EU
218 in the unilateral scenarios (F2F-50 and F2F-100). Implementing production-side policies in the EU27
219 led to slight increases in GHG emissions for non-EU countries (0.5%) in the F2F scenario, but these
220 were reversed when accompanied by dietary shifts in the multilateral scenarios (F2F-50m: -0.5%;
221 F2F-100m: -1.4%).

222 The F2F-50m and F2F-100m scenarios also resulted in 5.2 million (95% CI: 5 million, 5.4 million)
223 and 7.2 million (95% CI: 6.8 million, 7.5 million) averted deaths, representing a 6% and 8% reduction
224 in global deaths, respectively. The majority of averted deaths were in Eastern Europe, including
225 Ukraine (2.7 to 3 per 1000 people), Russia (2.3 to 2.8 per 1000 people), and Serbia (1.9 to 2.3 per
226 1000 people), followed by Cuba (5.9 to 6 per 1000 people), Barbados (1.7 to 2.1 per 1000 people),
227 and Trinidad and Tobago (each 1.7 to 2 per 1000 people) in the Caribbean (Figure 4 and
228 Supplementary Table S4). Most averted deaths in these countries were caused by reductions in
229 obesity. The smallest rates in averted deaths from diet- and weight-related risk factors were for
230 countries in Africa, reflecting the relatively lower rates of non-communicable disease mortality there.

231

232 **Discussion**

233 Our analysis provided quantitative estimates for the potential environmental and health impacts of
234 adopting F2F production- and consumption-side policies in the EU and worldwide. We found that
235 production-side policies alone contributed negligibly to diet-related reductions in mortality compared
236 to targeted dietary changes, and that targeted dietary changes also reinforced reductions to
237 environmental impacts achieved from production-side policies. Increasing vegetable consumption and

238 lowering obesity prevalence through reductions in total energy intake were found to contribute most
239 to averted deaths from coronary heart disease and cancer. While complete shifts towards
240 recommendations for healthy and sustainable diets resulted in the greatest number of averted deaths,
241 partial shifts also generated meaningful impacts (~80% of those from complete shifts) due to similar
242 reductions in total energy intake and in turn, deaths from weight-related risks, demonstrating the
243 importance of both the types and quantities of foods consumed in targeting reductions to premature
244 mortality. However, concrete consumption-side policies that would facilitate dietary change for
245 consumers would be required to realize the potential co-benefits across environmental and health
246 domains.

247 To our knowledge, this is the first analysis that assessed the potential impacts of F2F policies on both
248 environmental and health outcomes. The coupling of an agricultural economic model with a
249 comparative risk assessment allowed us to comprehensively assess changes in food consumption
250 influenced by a range of agricultural activities and concurrent reductions in premature mortality. Our
251 scenarios reflected F2F production-side policies with and without demand-side changes, which
252 revealed the importance of dietary changes for reducing environmental impacts from food systems
253 and improving population health. Our country-level health assessment demonstrated “hotspots” where
254 most impacts could be avoided through dietary shifts, and our sensitivity analysis accounted for
255 potential environmental and health impacts from partially adopting healthy and sustainable diets at a
256 global scale. Our results point to the efficacy of F2F policies for reducing environmental impacts and
257 improving population health, but only if coupled with strong demand-side policies that will aid in
258 facilitating the transition to healthy and sustainable diets for consumers.

259 Since the F2F strategy did not include quantitative targets for shifting diets, we developed scenarios
260 that combined quantitative production-side F2F targets with graded shifts towards healthy and
261 sustainable diets. Despite several strategies for dietary change proposed in the F2F strategy, including
262 nutrition labelling, sustainable food procurement, and VAT reform, none have been formally
263 implemented, and previous evidence indicates varying effectiveness. Information-based policy
264 instruments have been shown to be less effective than market-based and regulatory approaches for

265 changing behaviour.²⁸ A meta-analysis of consumer and industry responses to front-of-pack nutrition
266 labels revealed improvements for dietary intakes and product composition,²⁹ but poor understanding
267 of labels for individuals of low socioeconomic status could exacerbate health inequities in this
268 group.³⁰ Public food procurement has shown promise in improving the health and sustainability of
269 diets. For example, optimizing nutritionally adequate school meals reduced diet-incurred GHG
270 emissions by 40% in Sweden³¹, while modelling the extension of school meal programs to all children
271 at a global scale could prevent one million cases of non-communicable diseases per year.³²
272 Implementing taxes on unhealthy food products is another effective policy tool for improving dietary
273 health and sustainability. A systematic review found that increasing tax rates on foods high in fat, salt,
274 or sugar decreased sales and led to lower BMI, and that taxes were most often responded to by lower-
275 income groups.³³ In Europe, modelling lower VAT rates on fruits and vegetables and higher VAT
276 rates on meat and dairy led to a 3% reduction in mortality while improving environmental and
277 economic outcomes.³² Together with supply-side measures, stronger incentives for dietary change are
278 needed to improve public health as part of global and regional efforts to achieve net-zero.

279 Our findings are consistent with those of previous reports highlighting the importance of dietary
280 change for achieving production-side targets of the F2F strategy. Implementing agroecological
281 farming practices met relevant EU targets only when modelled in conjunction with adoption of
282 recommendations for healthy and sustainable diets and reductions in food waste.¹⁴ Similarly, adopting
283 healthy and sustainable diets together with land-use policy measures in the Green Deal supported
284 regional food production and reduced environmental impacts.¹⁶ The complementarity of consumption-
285 side measures with agricultural practices largely occurs due to reduced pressures on agricultural
286 inputs from reductions in demand for meat and dairy products. In our study, targeted dietary changes
287 not only reinforced supply-side measures for environmental targets, but accounted for nearly all
288 potential health gains. The demonstrative synergies among production- and consumption-side
289 measures requires harmonising policies for achieving environmental and health goals.

290 The potential outsourcing of environmental impacts from the EU to other regions in pursuit of EU
291 net-zero targets is a concern. Despite supply-side measures to decrease EU meat production in the

292 F2F scenario, we observed small demand-side changes in this scenario due increased imports of meat
293 products that precluded substantive reductions in consumption. To reduce “carbon leakage”, the
294 Green Deal’s Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism, implemented in 2026, imposes a levy on goods
295 imported to the EU, but does not currently include agri-food products.³⁴ However, border carbon
296 adjustments may not necessarily prevent countries from exporting high carbon intensity products,
297 such as meat, which could undermine global mitigation efforts.³⁵ Outsourcing impacts could also be
298 mitigated through global coordination of efforts towards adopting healthy diets and sustainable food
299 systems, as demonstrated by our sensitivity analysis of multilateral scenarios. Given the prominence
300 of international trade for agricultural commodities, including agri-food products in border carbon
301 adjustments and fostering international cooperation will be important for achieving global climate and
302 health objectives.

303 Our study has several limitations. First, the lack of quantitative targets for healthy and sustainable
304 diets has led to heterogeneous assumptions in modelling the dietary changes that might ensue from
305 adopting F2F policies.^{12–16} Here, we modelled partial and complete shifts towards EAT-Lancet
306 recommendations, a globally recognized set of scientific targets for healthy diets. However, these may
307 not necessarily reflect the types of dietary changes that would result from adopting specific policies in
308 a real-world scenario. Setting specific targets for consumption-side policies in the F2F strategy is
309 needed to more accurately model the associated impacts.

310 Second, dietary changes in the F2F-50 and F2F-100 scenarios were implemented in CAPRI as an
311 exogenous variable without accounting for concrete diet-related policy pathways. For example, the
312 scale of reductions in red meat intake is unlikely to occur without concrete policy measures in a real-
313 world scenario. Such measures would have additional price effects that would influence consumer
314 demand (e.g., reduce demand by increasing prices). Our scenario implementation of demand-side
315 measures abstracted from these mechanisms and isolated the impacts of and following dietary change.
316 Pathways for consumer behaviour need to be integrated more strongly into food systems models to
317 better represent consumer responses to food-related policies over time and to mitigate unintended
318 feedbacks.

319 Third, in the comparative risk assessment, we assumed causal relationships between risk factors and
320 diseases as evidenced from exposure-response functions with strong to moderate quality of evidence
321 from meta-analyses. However, we cannot rule out the possibility of residual confounding due the
322 observational nature of studies in which the relative risks were derived. Finally, the land-use changes
323 estimated in CAPRI may pose environmental consequences in non-agricultural sectors, but these were
324 not captured in the model. Most F2F elements tend to increase land scarcity, which may create further
325 incentives to convert natural lands or forest lands into agricultural land, necessitating dedicated land-
326 use regulations.

327

328 **Conclusion**

329 By coupling an agricultural economic model with a comparative risk assessment to assess the
330 potential environmental and health impacts of adopting F2F policies, we found that targeted dietary
331 changes worked synergistically with production-side policies to reduce environmental impacts from the
332 food system and contributed nearly all health benefits compared to indirect dietary changes from
333 production-side policies alone. Despite large potential environmental and health co-benefits from
334 adopting healthy and sustainable diets, the lack of clearly defined consumption-side policies in the
335 F2F strategy lends uncertainty to how consumer dietary patterns will change in response to future
336 agricultural policies. Concrete policies with quantitative targets for healthy and sustainable diets are
337 needed with which to integrate health and climate goals in the F2F strategy and global commitments
338 to net-zero.

339

340 **Declaration of interests:** The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

341 **Data sharing:** Data will be made available upon request to OA.

342 **Author contributions:** Data curation: OA and MS; formal analysis: OA; funding acquisition: MS and
343 CT; investigation: OA; methodology: MS and PW; project administration: MS and CT; software: OA,

344 MS, and PW; supervision: MS and CT; validation: OA and MS; visualization: OA; writing – original
345 draft: OA. All authors contributed to the conceptualization of the study, reviewing and editing of the
346 manuscript, had access to the underlying data, and approved the final manuscript for submission.

347 **Acknowledgements:** This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe
348 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101057131, Climate Action To
349 Advance HeaLthY Societies in Europe (CATALYSE) and from the UK Research and Innovation
350 (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10047417] as
351 part of the Horizon Europe HORIZON-HLTH-2021-ENVHLTH-02 call under grant agreement
352 number 101057131. MS also acknowledges funding from Wellcome Trust through a Career
353 Development Award (Award number: 225318/Z/22/Z), the BrightSpace project (Grant agreement
354 number: 101060075), and the ACT4CAP project (Grant agreement number: 101134874).

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Fig. 1 Changes in diet composition for Farm to Fork scenarios for the EU27 in 2050

Fig. 2 Averted deaths of Farm to Fork scenarios for the EU27 in 2050

Fig. 3 Averted deaths of Farm to Fork scenarios for the EU27 by cause (a) and by risk factor (b) in 2050

Fig. 4 Averted deaths of multilateral Farm to Fork scenarios in 2050

F2F

F2F-50

F2F-100

Averted deaths (per 1000 people) 0 1 2 3

Preprint not peer-reviewed

F2F-50m

F2F-100m

Averted deaths (per 1000 people) 1 2 3 4 5 6

Table 1. Description of model scenarios

Scenario	Production-side targets		Consumption-side targets		
	Farm to Fork policies ¹	Green Deal carbon price ²	Dietary shifts ³	Total energy intake ⁴	Reduction in food waste
Reference	–	–	–	Current	–
F2F	↓ 50% nitrogen surplus ↓ 20% mineral fertilisers	EUR 310/t CO ₂	–	Current	–
F2F-50	↓ 30% pesticides ↑ 25% land under organic farming	EUR 310/t CO ₂	50%	Balanced	15%
F2F-100	10% agricultural land with high-diversity landscape features	EUR 470/t CO ₂	100%	Balanced	20%

¹Farm to Fork policies include a 50% reduction in nitrogen surplus; 20% reduction in mineral fertilisers; at least a 30% reduction in pesticides; 25% increase in land under organic farming; and 10% of agricultural land with high-diversity landscape features. ²Carbon prices are expressed as EUR/t CO₂ in 2015-EUR and reflect consistent EU carbon price trajectories. ³Shifts in diet composition towards planetary health diet recommendations. ⁴Current energy intake represents average age- and sex-specific energy intakes for each country. Balanced energy intake reflect recommendations for healthy bodyweight for adults based on each country's population structure and assuming moderate levels of physical activity.

Table 2. Environmental impacts of the EU agricultural sector from Farm to Fork scenarios in 2050

	Reference scenario	F2F	F2F-50	F2F-100	F2F-50m	F2F-100m	F2F	F2F-50	F2F-100	F2F-50m	F2F-100m
	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	% change				
Agricultural GHG emissions, mt/y											
Global	7370	7307	7223	7152	3736	2945	-0.9%	-2.0%	-3.0%	-49.3%	-60.0%
EU27	370	275	257	253	253	245	-25.7%	-30.5%	-31.6%	-31.6%	-33.8%
Non-EU	7000	7032	6966	6899	3483	2700	0.5%	-0.5%	-1.4%	-50.2%	-61.4%
Agricultural land use, m ha											
Global	5386	5391	5389	5389	5385	5383	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	-0.1%
EU27	160	165	163	163	162	161	3.1%	1.9%	1.9%	1.3%	0.6%
Non-EU27	5226	5226	5226	5226	5223	5222	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	-0.1%	-0.1%
Agricultural methane emissions, 1000t											
Nitrogen surplus, kg N/ha	63.0	33.1	32.1	31.9	32.2	31.1	-47.5%	-49.0%	-49.4%	-48.9%	-50.6%
Phosphorus surplus, kg P/ha	6.4	3.9	3.5	3.4	3.6	3.3	-39.1%	-45.3%	-46.9%	-43.8%	-48.4%
Agricultural ammonium emissions, kt											
Total pesticides, g active ingredients/ha	2316	1794	1637	1578	1529	1362	-22.5%	-29.3%	-31.9%	-34.0%	-41.2%
Share of fallow land in UAAR, %											
Ruminant density on fodder area, LU/ha	4.0	6.1	6.0	5.7	6.5	2.1	2.0%	1.7%	2.5%	-1.9%	-2.0%
Ruminant density on fodder area, LU/ha											
	0.73	0.6	0.55	0.53	0.58	0.57	-17.8%	-24.7%	-27.4%	-20.5%	-21.9%

% change is relative to the reference scenario, which represent the expected food system trajectories before publication of the Green Deal and observed diets. Abbreviations: GHG, greenhouse gas; LU, land use; m ha, megahectare; mt, megatonnes; UAAR, utilizable agricultural area.

Research in Context

Evidence before this study

Previous studies quantified the impacts of Farm to Fork production-side policies on economic and environmental outcomes, without accounting for consumption-side changes relating to diets and food loss and waste. Other studies integrated production and consumption perspectives but did not assess health outcomes explicitly. Some evidence suggests that targeted dietary changes are important for achieving production-side targets of the Farm to Fork strategy.

Added value of this study

Here, we advanced the literature in two ways. First, we provided quantitative estimates of the potential impacts of Farm to Fork policies on environmental and health outcomes. Second, we developed scenarios that represent adoption of production- and consumption-side policies of the Farm to Fork strategy. Use of a food systems model allowed us to capture the full range of effects of Farm to Fork policies on dietary intakes and environmental impacts, and the comparative risk assessment allowed us to estimate the mortality impacts of indirect demand-side changes of production side-policies or targeted dietary changes of consumption-side policies of the Farm to Fork strategy.

Implications of all the available evidence

Facilitating shifts towards healthy and sustainable diets is needed in conjunction with production-side policies of the Farm to Fork strategy in order to realise co-benefits for human and planetary health. This will require integrating concrete demand-side policies with quantitative targets in future updates to the Farm to Fork strategy.